

NEW RESEARCH AVENUES, METROLOGIES, AND IDEAS FOR OPTIMIZING GLASS AND CARBON FIBER EPOXY/AMINE COMPOSITES¹

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ABSTRACT

After more than 70 years of research and development, fibrous composites have become essential lightweight structural materials. Their applications span renewable energy systems, fuel-efficient automotive transportation, cost-effective recovery of limited petroleum resources, and the reshoring of CHIPs manufacturing to the United States. Despite these advances and the reliance on composite databases, optimizing composite toughness and durability and the development of new systems still relies heavily on “predictive” modeling techniques, often in the absence of standardized micromechanics test methodologies. Dr William Chen of Advanced Semiconductor Engineering, Inc. recently noted that “Modeling without metrology is imagination.” The presentation associated with this proceedings paper will provide a concise yet critical review on the state-of-art of micro-composite testing and its potential for predicting composite failure. Emerging research avenues, novel metrologies, and innovative concepts aimed at overcoming the current gaps in critical standardized micromechanics data will be highlighted. These developments open new pathways for enhancing the performance, reliability, and application breadth of glass and carbon fiber epoxy/amine composites.

1 INTRODUCTION

Epoxies are widely used in fiber-reinforced plastic (FRPs) because of their high strength, high modulus, and good solvent resistance. However, these properties are often accompanied by brittleness, which has been associated with the immobility of the network structure and the associated susceptibility of the network to crack initiation and propagation. This inherent network brittleness has been found to limit the ability of the composite manufacturer to make structural FRPs that are tough and have a high glass transition temperature (T_g). Initial attempts to overcome this difficulty led to the following toughness paradigm: “A strong interfacial bond between the fiber and matrix is essential for high strength (longitudinal and transverse), interlaminar delamination toughness and durability. Conversely a weak interfacial bond is needed for tensile fracture toughness, since interface debonding (mode 2 crack propagation) contributes to the composite’s energy absorption capability.”[1-6] Thus, high-strength and high-toughness are often mutually exclusive in the production of FRPs.[7, 8]

The 1972 research of Sharpe [9] introduced the concept that there exists a region between the fiber and matrix called an interphase that must be optimized if tough high- T_g FRPs are to be manufactured. To overcome the FRP strength-toughness dichotomy, the Air Force Wright Aeronautical Laboratories [10-12] and the National Aeronautics and Space Administration (NASA) Langley Research Center

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(LRC) [13-15] initiated separate research projects and workshops focused on the fiber-matrix (F-M) interphase and the toughening of the thermoset resin, respectively. After decades of research,[16] NASA-LRC concluded that the ideal matrix for enhancing FRP toughness must have the following properties:

- (a) Young's Modulus (E_V^m) > 3.10 GPa
- (b) Shear Modulus (G^m) > 1.38 GPa
- (c) Tensile and Shear Strengths > 110 MPa
- (d) Matrix Strain-to-Failure (ϵ_f^m) \geq 8 %
- (e) Mode I Matrix Composite Toughness (G_{1c}^m) > 700 J/m²

Because the interphase is embedded between the fiber and matrix and formed during the composite manufacturing process, developing measurement techniques that 1) quantify the F-M interfacial shear strength (IFSS), 2) determine the mechanical properties (e.g., modulus), which enhances strength, and 3) provide insight and guidelines for achieving the desired fracture morphology have proven to be challenging. Since the inception of a composites research group at the National Institute of Standards and Technology (NIST) in 1989 extensive research has been conducted on developing an accurate measurement technology to quantify the F-M IFSS based on the single fiber fragmentation test (SFFT) and answer the following fundamental questions:

- (a) How can the F-M IFSS obtained from the SFFT exceed the shear yield stress (\approx 40 MPa) of the often-used diglycidyl ether of bisphenol-A/meta-phenylenediamine (DGEBA/m-PDA) matrix and other thermoset matrices?
- (b) Can a F-M IFSS be obtained using thermoset matrices that do not have a ϵ_f^m that is three-to-five times the failure strain of the fiber (ϵ_f^f)?

Given the complex nature of the F-M interphase formation during the composite manufacturing process, these research questions can only be answered by addressing the following targeted research areas:

- (a) A critical assessment of the current SFFT and its assumptions.
- (b) A critical investigation of the F-M interphase through controlled molecular architecture (CMA) studies and determination of the chemistry perturbations that occur in the F-M interphase region that result in its properties being different from the bulk resin.
- (c) Fundamental studies of the dynamics of the stress-redistribution process associated with fiber fracture, as the time-scale for the stress-redistribution occurs on the order of 50 ns.[17]
- (d) Develop a fundamental understanding of the yield behavior of thermoset resin used to manufacture structural FRPs.

In this report and presentation, a summary of these findings and their impact on the current SFFT will be presented. In particular, the primary finding is that many of the thermoset matrices that are used in the manufacture of FRPs do not undergo macroscopic tensile yielding during the SFFT, even though ϵ_f^m may be as high as 10 %. Thus, many of the thermoset matrices used in the SFFT regime deforms as a nonlinear anelastic material. Therefore, the reported F-M IFSS values can exceed the "apparent" shear yield stress of the matrix since the matrix does not undergo macroscopic yield. Additionally, the absence of macroscopic yield allows the F-M IFSS values to be obtained from the first few fiber breaks rather than deforming the SFFT specimen to saturation.

2 TARGETED RESEARCH AREAS

2.1 Critical Assessment of the Current SFFT

The SFFT that is used to assess the F-M IFSS in FRP was adapted [18-21] with modifications from the metal matrix composites (MMCs) research of Kelly and Tyson (K-T model).[22, 23] The equation for calculating the F-M IFSS is shown in Equation 1.

Equation 1

$$\frac{l_c}{d_f} = \frac{\sigma_f(l_c)}{2\tau_{IFSS}}$$

This equation is based on the following assumptions: (a) that the matrix deforms in an elastic-perfectly plastic manner, (b) perfect bonding exists at the F-M interface (i.e., no evidence of debonding along the fiber away from the fiber fracture), (c) the transfer of stress from the matrix to the fiber occurs by shear only, and (d) the value of τ_{IFSS} is limited by the shear yield strength of the matrix. Because of the strength/length dependence of carbon and glass fibers, Bascom and Jensen [24] concluded that the fiber strength (σ_f) must be determined at the critical transfer length (l_c). Thus, $\sigma_f(l_c)$ is used in Equation 1 rather than σ_f , which has a definitive value in MMCs. This necessitated that the fiber must be repeatedly fractured until the fracture process ceased (saturation) and the average of the fragment lengths at saturation ($\langle l_{sat} \rangle$) be multiplied by a factor (usually (4/3)) to obtain l_c .

$$l_c = \frac{4}{3} \langle l_{sat} \rangle$$

Furthermore, since l_c is generally $< 1,000 \mu m$, $\sigma_f(l_c)$ must be obtained from the SFFT data. DiBenedetto et al.[18] noted that because the repeated fracture process truncated the distribution strength at the required length, determining $\sigma_f(l_c)$ from the SFFT data would not be straight forward. In addition, Holmes et al.[25] found that since the break locations during the repeated fracture process evolved to a uniform distribution, the extraction of reliable Weibull parameters to determine $\sigma_f(l_c)$ was not feasible.

Galiotis [26] in his investigation of carbon and Kevlar fiber/epoxy microcomposites using laser Raman spectroscopy (LRS) found that a F-M IFSS value could be obtained by measuring the strain profile in the Raman active carbon or Kevlar fiber and fitting the data to a polynomial equation. Interestingly, he obtained from his model independent approach a F-M IFSS value (62 MPa) for the Kevlar fiber/epoxy microcomposite that easily exceeded the estimated DGEBA/m-PDA shear yield stress of 30 MPa (Tresca) or 35 MPa (von Mises) (Figure 1). Even more interesting, he found that the strain profile (Figure 1) was consistent with the Cox shear-lag model rather than the K-T model used in MMCs. In the development of the SFFT for FRPs, DiBenedetto [18, 20, 24] suggested that the F-M IFSS value should be considered a F-M stress transfer coefficient that reflects the efficiency of the stress transfer process at the F-M interphase, thereby avoiding the apparent conflict caused by τ_{IFSS} exceeding the value of the apparent shear yield stress of the matrix.

Figure 1. Reconstructed 1 % strain and shear data as determined by laser Raman spectroscopy (LRS) of the Kevlar-49/Ciba-Geigy 1927 single fiber test specimen with strain and shear profiles predicted by Cox model (Adapted from [26]).

2.2 Critical Investigation of F-M Interphase Formation in E-Glass/DGEBA/m-PDA Composites

From early in the 1970s, there was a consensus that the stress transfer between the fiber and matrix resulted from tractions established in the F-M interphase region. These tractions were rationalized to be due to physicochemical interactions (τ_{PCI}), mechanical interlocking (τ_{MI}), and covalent bonding (τ_{CB}). In 1987, Nardin and Ward [27] codified the F-M IFSS as being the additive sum of these accepted tractions (Equation 2).

Equation 2

$$\tau_{IFSS} = \tau_{PCI} + \tau_{MI} + \tau_{CB}$$

In 1983, Drzal et al.[11, 12] established that τ_{IFSS} in carbon fiber/epoxy/amine composites is primarily due to τ_{MI} with about 15 % arising from τ_{CB} . Therefore, at a given temperature, which keeps the matrix constant, the τ_{MI} density affects the efficiency of the stress transfer process.

Holmes et al.[28-31] engineered F-M interphases for glass fiber/epoxy/amine composites that isolated the contribution of each traction component by using a CMA approach. To achieve this goal the covalent bonding density was varied by depositing on the glass fiber surface silane coupling agents (SCAs) that contained various amounts of non-bonding (alkyl) and bonding (amine functionalized) SCAs. Since, the aqueous deposition process yields a rough sizing layer, self-assembled monolayer technology, which is non-aqueous, was employed to provide a smooth sizing layer on the glass surface, thereby eliminating the τ_{MI} traction. By using the SFFT to monitor the number of fiber breaks at saturation and hence, the change in the F-M IFSS, plots of the number of fiber breaks from the various compositions and deposition processes are shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2. Comparison of the number of fiber breaks and hence the change in F-M IFSS obtained during the SFFT of E-glass fiber treated with aqueous and non-aqueous depositions of APTMS/PTMS and SAM deposition of 11-AUTCS/UTCS (Adapted from [30]).

In Figure 2, the aqueous deposition of propyl trimethoxysilane (PTMS) and γ -aminopropyl trimethoxysilane (APTMS) solutions exhibit a non-uniform increase in the number of fiber breaks at saturation (and hence, F-M IFSS) as the concentration of APTMS in the solution increases from 0 % to 100 %. In addition, the fracture morphology changed from debonding, when only the silane solution contains 100 % PTMS (i.e., only $\tau_{PCI} + \tau_{MI}$ tractions exist in the F-M interphase region), to debonding with matrix crack formation, when the silane solution contains 100 % APTMS (i.e., $\tau_{PCI} + \tau_{MI} + \tau_{CB}$ tractions exist in the F-M interphase). To remove the τ_{MI} traction from the F-M interphase, self-assembled monolayers (SAMs) composed of undecane trichlorosilane (UTCS, a non-bonding SCA) and 11-aminoundecane trichlorosilane (AUTCS, a bonding SCA) were deposited on the glass surface. Unlike the aqueous deposition of PTMS/APTMS solutions, the F-M IFSS for the UTCS/AUTCS solutions consistently increases with amine concentration on the glass fiber surface, but at about 33 % amine group concentration the rate of the F-M IFSS changes. This rate change is due to steric factors since the phenyl group on the DGEBA molecule is much larger than the amine groups on the fiber surface and effectively shields two additional amine groups when the DGEBA molecule reacts. However, like the PTMS/APTMS solutions, the fracture morphology in the UTCS/AUTCS SAMs also changes from debonding only, to debonding with matrix cracking as the concentration of amines increases.

Interestingly, the F-M IFSS is much higher in the SAMs than in the aqueous deposition sizing composed of PTMS/APTMS. This difference in F-M IFSS, denoted by the question mark in Figure 2, is due to the aminopropyl group on γ -aminopropyl triethoxysilane (APTES) and APTMS being oriented toward the glass surface during the aqueous deposition process.[32, 33] Therefore, the misoriented SCAs are not available for covalent bonding with DGEBA during the composite formation process. Support for this finding is shown for PTMS/APTMS deposited on the glass surface from the non-aqueous solution (SAMs Aminopropyl in Figure 2). Consistent with the short propyl chains not forming a SAM, at zero percent covalent bonding shear stress is transferred by τ_{MI} , but to a lesser extent than from the aqueous deposition process. However, at amine concentrations ≥ 25 %, the number of fiber breaks (i.e., F-M IFSS) are comparable to those of the UTCS/AUTCS SAMs.

More importantly, these data show that τ_{PCI} and τ_{MI} alone or together do not result in the fracture morphology changing from debonding only to debonding with matrix crack formation. This change in fracture morphology is due to the increase in covalent bond density (i.e., τ_{CB}). Since aliphatic amines react with DGEBA at room temperature, the CMA studies - especially from the SAMs studies - indicate that the DGEBA molecules are oriented almost perpendicular to the surface when they react on the amine-sized glass surfaces. The randomization of the polymer chains that may be capable of thwarting a growing matrix crack occurs some distance away from the E-glass fiber surface. This further implies that to control the fracture morphology, the τ_{CB} must be moderated in the F-M interphase region, or the bulk matrix toughness must be increased to thwart the growth of matrix cracks during the fiber fracture process.

In 2010, Holmes et al. [34] prevented the premature failure of combinatorial multi-fiber fragmentation test specimens composed of APTES sized E-glass by replacing DGEBA in the often used DGEBA/m-PDA matrix with an 80/20 wt. % blend of DGEBA and diglycidyl ether of 1,4-butanediol (DGEBD, RD-2², reactive diluent). [Although mass % rather than wt. % is the proper terminology, wt. % will be used throughout this paper to minimize confusion to the reader, since wt. % is pervasive throughout the FRP literature.] Reactive diluents are routinely used in the manufacture of FRPs to lower the DGEBA resin viscosity ($\approx 12,000$ cP at 25 °C) to 800 cP. This approach is widely used to facilitate wetting and interpenetration of the resin between the fibers during the manufacturing process. In addition to reducing the viscosity, it was found that adding the DGEBD resin increased the strain-to-failure (ϵ_f^m) of the DGEBA/m-PDA network from ≈ 6 % to ≈ 10 %, with no reduction in Young's

² Certain commercial equipment, instruments, or materials are identified in this document. Such identification does not imply recommendation or endorsement by NIST, nor does it imply that the products identified are necessarily the best available for the purpose.

modulus (E_Y^m) and an apparent increase in the tensile yield stress of the matrix. A subsequent paper by McCarthy et al. [35] revealed that at saturation the single fibers in the combinatorial specimens, contained ≈ 50 breaks with no apparent yielding near the fragment ends where the shear stress is the highest, while ≈ 40 breaks occurred in the 6 fiber array due to interaction between the fibers. A distortion in the matrix surrounding the colinear fiber breaks was observed and attributed to yielding caused by the more complicated shear stress state between the interacting fibers (Figure 3). Since no fundamental research had been conducted on the impact of adding DGEBD to the DGEBA/m-PDA matrix, a research effort was initiated to understand the basis for matrix crack suppression during fiber fracture, as well as the feasibility of incorporating this flexible DGEBD diepoxide into the DGEBA/m-PDA network without compromising mechanical properties - especially since the oligomer content in DGEBD is extremely high ($\approx 40\%$) and would be expected to result in a network with lower crosslink density.[36, 37] It is worth noting that the colinear breaks in the fiber array are subcritical cracks and for these cracks to coalesce into a critical crack the matrix ligaments must fracture. This delayed coalescence is expected to increase the composite's toughness.

Figure 3. Fiber breaks from a combinatorial test specimen that contains 2 isolated single fibers and a 6-fiber array of closely spaced fibers (Adapted from [35]).

2.3 Fundamental Studies of the Dynamic Stress Redistribution Process during Fiber Fracture

In 1977, Ovchinskii et al. [38, 39] in their research of MMCs noted that the study of composite failure processes requires an investigation of the dynamic stress-redistribution process that occurs in local volumes surrounding the site of fiber breaks. Since this stress redistribution process occurs on the order of 50 ns , this phenomenon has been investigated primarily from a theoretical and finite element perspective.[17] To address this challenge, Woodcock et al. [40] developed a novel rhodamine based molecular probe that is activated mechanically and by UV light after it is integrated into an epoxy/amine network. Using fluorescence lifetime imaging microscopy (FLIM) to detect changes in the lifetime of the matrix surrounding the molecular probe, they found for the amine-sized E-glass fibers embedded in a DGEBA (80 wt. %)/DGEBD (20 wt. %)/m-PDA network that shear yielding did not occur in the SFFT specimen at the fragment ends where the shear stress is the highest. Instead, they observed a change in fluorescence lifetime several fiber diameters away from the fiber break (Figure 4). This surprising finding was linked to the dynamic fiber fracture process which generates a compressive shear wave that propagates down the fiber and yields the matrix.

Figure 4. Comparison of a fiber break visualized optically (left image) and by fluorescence lifetime imaging microscopy (FLIM, right image). The change in lifetime 3 to 5 fiber diameters from the fiber break is associated with matrix yielding caused by the compressive wave generated during the fiber fracture event. (Adapted from [40])

2.4 Probing the “Apparent” Yield Behavior of DGEBA/Amine Matrices

The absence of tension induced shear yielding at the fragment ends was found to be consistent with prior research by Feillard et al. [41, 42] who noted that DGEBA and the DGEBA (80 wt. %)/DGEBD (20 wt. %) blend when cured with diaminodiphenylmethane (DDM) rather than the m-PDA that is used in this study does not undergo macroscopic yielding in tension even after being deformed to $\approx 8\%$ strain. Consistent with these findings, the DGEBA/m-PDA matrix after being strained during the SFFT to 4.2 % has only 0.2 % strain remaining after unloading.[43, 44] To further demonstrate the recovery of epoxy/amine networks, the DGEBA (80 wt. %)/DGEBD (20 wt. %)/m-PDA network was loaded to 5.5 % and unloaded three times (Figure 5). These data suggests that these matrices do not yield during the SFFT, but rather deform in a nonlinear anelastic manner.

Figure 5. Repeated deformation up to 5.5 % and viscoelastic recovery of the DGEBA (80 wt. %)/DGEBD (20 wt. %)/m-PDA matrix. Complete viscoelastic recovery indicates nonlinear anelastic deformation behavior.

2.5 A New Methodology for Determining the F-M IFSS in E-Glass/DGEBA/Amine Matrices

Since the DGEBA/amine networks undergo macroscopic yield, the F-M IFSS can be determined by deforming the SFFT specimen enough to cause a few breaks in the fiber (typically, less than five) and then measuring the lengths of each fragment under stress and again after the deformation has been removed.[45] The average strain obtained from these measurements is then fit to the following equation by (a) dividing the fragment lengths by $1 \mu\text{m}$ subdivisions (e.g., if the fragment has a length of $348.59 \mu\text{m}$, then $N = 348$), (b) setting $r_m \approx 10r_f$, and (c) adjusting $E_m^{secant}\{\varepsilon, t\}$ until the values match.

Equation 3

$$\langle \varepsilon_f\{z, \varepsilon, t\} \rangle_{measured} = \frac{E^*}{N} \varepsilon \sum_{i=0}^N \left[1 - \frac{\cosh \beta^{secant}\{\varepsilon, t\} \left(\frac{l}{2} - z_N \right)}{\cosh \beta^{secant}\{\varepsilon, t\} \frac{l}{2}} \right]$$

where

N denotes the number of calculations made along the fiber

$$E^* = \frac{(E_f - E_m^{secant}\{\varepsilon, t\})}{E_f}$$

$$\beta^{secant}\{\varepsilon, t\} = \frac{1}{r_f} \left[\frac{E_m^{secant}\{\varepsilon, t\}}{(1 + \nu_m)(E_f - E_m^{secant}\{\varepsilon, t\}) \ln \left(\frac{r_m}{r_f} \right)} \right]^{1/2}$$

Once $E_m^{secant}\{\varepsilon, t\}$ is obtained, a plot of the shear stress using the following equation readily gives the F-M IFSS at the fragment ends (i.e., $z = 0$):

Equation 4

$$\tau_{f-m}\{z, \varepsilon, t\} = \frac{r_f \beta\{\varepsilon, t\} \sigma_c}{2} \left(\frac{E_f - E_m\{\varepsilon, t\}}{E_m\{\varepsilon, t\}} \right) \left[\frac{\sinh \beta\{\varepsilon, t\} \left(\frac{l}{2} - z \right)}{\cosh \beta\{\varepsilon, t\} \frac{l}{2}} \right]$$

Examples of calculations from the first few breaks in a SFFT specimen are shown in Table 1.

Table 1. Calculation of $\tau_{(ISS)}$ using initial fragments in Bare2_9 (Adapted from [45]).

Fragment Size, μm	Global Strain	$\tau_{(ISS)}$, MPa	Fragment $E_m^{secant}\{\varepsilon, t\}$ from Equation 9, GPa	Global Secant $E_m^{secant}\{\varepsilon, t\}$, GPa	% Change from Global Secant
7,710.49	0.021	67.1	2.437	2.299	+6 %
2,415.98	0.021	68.7	2.323	2.299	+1 %
3,160.02	0.021	64.9	2.591	2.299	+13 %
3,306.41	0.021	71.8	2.133	2.299	-7 %
980.09	0.021	72.6	2.088	2.299	-13 %

3 CONCLUSIONS

From a critical review of the SFFT and its assumptions, it is shown that the appropriate shear-lag model for calculating the F-M IFSS is a Cox-type model and not the K-T model that is often used. Additionally, a critical look at the tractions that are formed at the F-M interphase indicates that although mechanical interlocking (τ_{MI}) and physicochemical (τ_{PCI}) interactions occur, the degree of covalent bonding (τ_{CB}) controls the fiber fracture morphology and enhances the stress transfer efficiency of the load between the matrix and the reinforcing fiber. Interestingly, for an amine-sized glass fiber, the initial reaction of the epoxy with the SCA suggests that the reacting chain grows perpendicular from the fiber surface, indicating that the resistance to matrix crack propagation in the interphase region is very low and that the bulk matrix must be toughened to minimize matrix crack growth. The observation that adding the DGEBD reactive diluent to the DGEBA/m-PDA network can thwart matrix crack growth indicates that there is a fundamental property - or set of matrix properties - that may be quantifiable and predictive of its performance in FRPs. The nonlinear anelastic deformation of the DGEBA/amine matrix suggests that if other thermosets exhibit similar behavior, the F-M IFSS can be determined without requiring the matrix to have a high extension to failure strain.

Finally, the average strain approach for assessing the F-M IFSS in glass fiber/epoxy/amine microcomposites mirrors the LRS strain profile measurements made by Galiotis for carbon fiber/epoxy/amine microcomposites. Using the LRS approach he determined the F-M IFSS without the need of deforming the specimen to saturation. The research of Drzal et al. showed that carbon fibers are coated with a DGEBA sizing (EPON 1001F) that is devoid of an amine curing agent. Based on chemistry considerations, the F-M interphase that is formed during the composite manufacturing process is off stoichiometric in the epoxide rich direction due to the limited diffusion of m-PDA into this sizing layer. Thus, this rigid but brittle interphase is also not capable of thwarting a growing crack during the fiber fracture event, unless τ_{MI} is extremely low as in high modulus carbon fibers.

In apparent contrast, atomic force microscopy research [46] of the F-M interphase formed on carbon fiber/DGEBA/PACM 20 SFFT specimen have suggested that when stoichiometric amounts of the PACM 20 amine curing agent are used to cure DGEBA, the cycloaliphatic amine has enough time to diffuse throughout the DGEBA sizing so that there is a stoichiometric amount of amine reacting at each point throughout the sizing. Based a diffusion-reaction kinetics model, the gradient predicted by Drzal in the carbon fiber/DGEBA/m-PDA SFFT specimen does not seem to occur in the carbon fiber/DGEBA/PACM 20 SFFT specimen. Because the performance of the F-M interphase in the carbon fiber/DGEBA/PACM 20 SFFT specimen was not correlated to fiber fracture morphology no additional inferences can be made about this F-M interphase performance. However, the Drzal research teaches that matrix cracks do form when moderate modulus (AS) carbon fibers are embedded in the DGEBA/m-PDA matrix. These results underscore the need of researchers to think of the F-M interphase and bulk matrix as a system that must be optimized to control the fracture morphology during fiber fracture. Thus, future research will continue to focus on achieving a better understanding of the DGEBA/DGEBD/m-PDA network's molecular dynamics during high strain rate deformation events such as fiber fracture.

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REFERENCES AND NOTES

- [1] B.D. Agarwal, L.J. Broutman, Analysis and Performance of Fiber Composites, 2nd ed., John Wiley & Sons, New York, 1990.
- [2] J.K. Kim, Y.W. Mai, Engineered Interfaces in Fiber Reinforced Composites, 1st ed., Elsevier, Amsterdam, 1998.

- [3] K.D. Jones, A.T. Dibenedetto, Fiber Fracture in Hybrid Composite Systems, *Composites Science and Technology* 51(1) (1994) 53-62.
- [4] C.Y. Yue, W.L. Cheung, The Morphology, Character and Strength of the Interface in Glass-Fiber Polypropylene Composites, *Journal of Materials Science* 26(4) (1991) 870-880.
- [5] H.-Y. Liu, Y.-W. Mai, An appraisal of composite interface mechanics models and some challenging problems, *Composite Interfaces* 6(4) (1998) 343-362.
- [6] M.S. Madhukar, L.T. Drzal, Fiber-Matrix Adhesion and Its Effect on Composite Mechanical-Properties.4. Mode-I and Mode-II Fracture-Toughness of Graphite Epoxy Composites, *Journal of Composite Materials* 26(7) (1992) 936-968.
- [7] A.G. Atkins, Intermittent Bonding for High Toughness - High-Strength Composites, *Journal of Materials Science* 10(5) (1975) 819-832.
- [8] R.O. Ritchie, The conflicts between strength and toughness, *Nature Materials* 10(11) (2011) 817-822.
- [9] L.H. Sharpe, The Interphase in Adhesion, *Journal of Adhesion* 4(1) (1972) 51-64.
- [10] L.T. Drzal, Summary of the Workshop Held on the Role of the Polymer-Substrate Interphase in Structural Adhesion, in: U.o.D.R. Institute (Ed.) Air Force Materials Laboratory, Ohio, 1977.
- [11] L.T. Drzal, M.J. Rich, P.F. Lloyd, Adhesion of Graphite fibers to Epoxy Matrices: 1. The Role of Fiber Surface Treatments, *Journal of Adhesion* 16(1) (1983) 1-30.
- [12] L.T. Drzal, M.J. Rich, M.F. Koenig, P.F. Lloyd, Adhesion of Graphite Fibers to Epoxy Matrices: II. The Effect of Fiber Finish, *Journal of Adhesion* 16(2) (1983) 133-152.
- [13] L.F. Vosteen, N.J. Johnston, L.A. Teichman, Tough Composite Materials, NASA Langley Research Center 1983.
- [14] N.J. Johnston, Toughened Composites, ASTM, Philadelphia, PA, 1987.
- [15] M.D. Rhodes, J.G. Williams, J.H. Starnes, Effect of Low Velocity Impact Damage on the Compressive Strength of Graphite/Epoxy Hat-Stiffened Panels, NASA TN D-8411, 1977.
- [16] D.R. Tenney, J.G. Davis Jr., R.B. Pipes, N.J. Johnston, NASA Composite Materials Development: Lessons Learned and Future Challenges, Support of Composite Systems, Bonn, Germany, AVT 164, 2009, pp. 1-58.
- [17] R. Ganesh, S. Sockalingam, B.Z. Haque, J.W. Gillespie, Dynamic effects of single fiber break in unidirectional glass fiber-reinforced composites, *Journal of Composite Materials* 51(9) (2017) 1307-1320.
- [18] W.A. Fraser, F.H. Ancker, A.T. DiBenedetto, A Computer Modeled, Single Filament Technique for Measuring Coupling and Sizing Agent Effects in Fiber Reinforced Composites, The Society of the Plastics Industry, Inc., 1975, pp. 1-13.
- [19] A.T. Dibenedetto, D.A. Scola, Characterization of S-Glass-Polymer Interfaces Using Ion Scattering Spectroscopy and Scattered Ion Mass-Spectroscopy, *Journal of Colloid and Interface Science* 64(3) (1978) 480-500.
- [20] W.A. Fraser, F.H. Ancker, A.T. DiBenedetto, B. Elbirli, Evaluation of Surface Treatments for Fibers in Composite-Materials, *Polymer Composites* 4(4) (1983) 238-248.
- [21] L.T. Drzal, M.J. Rich, J.D. Camping, W.J. Park, Interfacial Shear Strength and Failure Mechanisms in Graphite Fiber Composites, Reinforced Plastics/Composites Institute and The Society of the Plastics Industry, Inc., 1980, pp. 1-7.
- [22] A. Kelly, W.R. Tyson, Tensile Properties of Fibre-Reinforced Metals: Copper/Tungsten and Copper/Molybdenum, *J Mech Phys Solids* 13 (1965) 329-350.

- [23] A. Kelly, W.R. Tyson, Fiber-Strengthened Materials, in: V.F. Zackay (Ed.), High-Strength Materials, John Wiley & Sons, Inc., New York, 1965, pp. 578-602.
- [24] W.D. Bascom, R.M. Jensen, Stress Transfer in Single Fiber/Resin Tensile Tests, *Journal of Adhesion* 19(3-4) (1986) 219-239.
- [25] J. Kim, S. Leigh, G. Holmes, E-Glass/DGEBA/m-PDA Single Fiber Composites: New Insights into the Statistics of F Fiber Fragmentation, *Journal of Polymer Science Part B-Polymer Physics* 47(23) (2009) 2301-2312.
- [26] C. Galiotis, Interfacial Studies on Model Composites by Laser Raman-Spectroscopy, *Composites Science and Technology* 42(1-3) (1991) 125-150.
- [27] M. Nardin, I.M. Ward, Influence of Surface-Treatment on Adhesion of Polyethylene Fibers, *Materials Science and Technology* 3(10) (1987) 814-816.
- [28] E. Feresenbet, D. Raghavan, G.A. Holmes, Application of Self Assembled Monolayer Approach to Probe Fiber Matrix-Adhesion, in: A. Karim, T.P. Russell, C.W. Frank, P.F. Nealey (Eds.) *Materials Research Society, Warrendale,PA, 2002*, pp. 167-172.
- [29] E. Feresenbet, D. Raghavan, G.A. Holmes, The Influence of Silane Coupling Agent Composition on the Surface Characterization of Fiber and on Fiber-Matrix Interfacial Shear Strength, *The Journal of Adhesion* 79(7) (2003) 643-665.
- [30] G.A. Holmes, E. Feresenbet, D. Raghavan, Using Self-Assembled Monolayer Technology to Probe the Mechanical Response of the Fiber Interphase-Matrix Interphase Interface, *Composite Interfaces* 10(6) (2003) 515-546.
- [31] E. Feresenbet, D. Raghavan, G.A. Holmes, The Role of the Terminal Functional Group of Self-Assembled Monolayers on Fiber Matrix Adhesion, *Journal of Applied Polymer Science* 106(1) (2007) 462-469.
- [32] C.H. Chiang, H. Ishida, J.L. Koenig, The Structure of γ -Aminopropyltriethoxysilane on Glass Surfaces, *Journal of Colloid and Interface Science* 74(2) (1980) 396-404.
- [33] F.J. Boerio, L. Armogan, S.Y. Cheng, Structure of γ -Aminopropyltriethoxysilane Films on Iron Mirrors, *Journal of Colloid and Interface Science* 73(2) (1980) 416-424.
- [34] G.A. Holmes, J.H. Kim, S. Leigh, W. McDonough, The Single Fiber Composite Test: A Comparison of E-Glass Fiber Fragmentation Data with Statistical Theories, *Journal of Applied Polymer Science* 117(1) (2010) 509-516.
- [35] E.D. McCarthy, J.H. Kim, N.A. Heckert, S.D. Leigh, J.W. Gilman, G.A. Holmes, The Fiber Break Evolution Process in a 2-D Epoxy/Glass Multi-Fiber Array, *Composites Science and Technology* 121 (2015) 73-81.
- [36] J.W. Woodcock, S.J. Stranick, A.P. Kotula, S.H. Chen, S. Engmann, J.W. Gilman, G.A. Holmes, Reaction-Induced structural and compositional heterogeneity in amine-cured epoxy/epoxy thermosets: Visualization of heterogeneity using fluorescence lifetime imaging microscopy (FLIM), *Polymer* 273 (2023).
- [37] A.P. Kotula, J.W. Woodcock, J.W. Gilman, G.A. Holmes, A cure kinetics investigation of amine-cured epoxy by Rheo-Raman spectroscopy, *Polymer* 278 (2023) 125967.
- [38] A.S. Ovchinskii, I.M. Kop'ev, E.N. Sakharova, V.V. Moskvitin, Stress Redistribution upon Breakage of Brittle Fibers in Metallic Composite Materials, *Polymer Mechanics: A translation of Mekhanika Polimerov* 13(1) (1977) 16-26.
- [39] A.S. Ovchinskii, E.N. Sakharova, Dynamics of Stress Redistribution in a Ruptured Fiber of a Composite Material, *Mechanics of Composite Materials (A translation of Mekhanika Kompozitnykh Materialov)* 15(1) (1979) 45-51.
- [40] J.W. Woodcock, R.J. Sheridan, R. Beams, S.J. Stranick, W.F. Mitchell, L.C. Brinson, V. Gudapati, D. Hartman, A. Vaidya, J.W. Gilman, G.A. Holmes, Damage Sensing Using a Mechanophore Crosslinked Epoxy Resin in Single-Fiber Composites, *Composites Science and Technology* (2020).

- [41] P. Feillard, G. Desarmot, J.P. Favre, A Critical-Assessment of the Fragmentation Test for Glass Epoxy Systems, *Composites Science And Technology* 49(2) (1993) 109-119.
- [42] P. Feillard, D. Rouby, G. Desarmot, J.P. Farve, Limits of Conventional Micromechanical Analysis of Interface Properties in Glass Epoxy Model Composites, *Materials Science and Engineering A-Structural Materials Properties Microstructure and Processing* 188(1-2) (1994) 159-166.
- [43] G.A. Holmes, R.C. Peterson, D.L. Hunston, W.G. McDonough, E-glass/DGEBA/m-PDA Single Fiber Composites: The Effect of Strain Rate on Interfacial Shear Strength Measurements, *Polymer Composites* 21(3) (2000) 450-465.
- [44] J.H. Kim, S.D. Leigh, G. Holmes, E-Glass/DGEBA/m-PDA Single Fiber Composites: New Insights into the Statistics of Fiber Fragmentation, *Journal of Polymer Science Part B* 47(23) (2009) 2301-2312.
- [45] G. Holmes, L.A.A. Powell, A Non-Saturation Approach for Obtaining the Fiber-Matrix Interfacial Shear Strength in Glass Fiber Composites, *SAMPE Journal* 61(1) (2025) 20-28.
- [46] M.R. VanLandingham, R.R. Dagastine, R.F. Eduljee, R.L. McCullough, J.W. Gillespie, Characterization of nanoscale property variations in polymer composite systems: 1. Experimental results, *Composites Part a-Applied Science and Manufacturing* 30(1) (1999) 75-83.